

Interventional, randomised, open label, multi-centre, parallel-group, controlled study
investigating the effects of using the PReDicT Test to guide the antidepressant treatment
of depressed patients

Statistical Analysis Plan

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ADE	Adverse Device Effect
AE	Adverse Event
CEAC	Cost-Effectiveness Acceptability Curve
CIP	Clinical Investigation Plan
eCRF	Electronic Case Report Form
ePRO	Electronic Patient Reported Outcomes
DSST	Digit Symbol Substitution Test
GAD-7	Generalised Anxiety Disorder Questionnaire, 7 item version
EQ-5D-5L	Five dimensional – 5 Level quality of life questionnaire
GCP	Good Clinical Practice
GP-ETB	General Practitioner-P1vital® Oxford Emotional Test Battery
HEQ	Health Economics Questionnaire
ICF	Informed Consent Form
MADRS	Montgomery–Åsberg Depression Rating Scale
OxCAP-MH	Oxford CAPabilities questionnaire-Mental Health
PIS	Participant Information Sheet
PReDicT Test	Predicting Response to Depression Treatment Test
QIDS-SR-16	Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology - Self Report
SAS-SR (screeener version)	Social Adjustment Scale – Self-Report (screeener version)
SSRI	Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitor
TaU	Treatment as Usual
SAE	Serious Adverse Event
SADE	Serious Adverse Device Effect
SD	Standard Deviation

SUSARs	Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reactions
UK	United Kingdom
USADE	Unanticipated Serious Adverse Device Effect

1. INTRODUCTION & PURPOSE

This document details the rules proposed and the presentation that will be followed, as closely as possible, when analysing and reporting the main clinical effectiveness results from the interventional, randomised, open label, multi-centre, parallel-group, controlled study investigating the effects of using the PReDicT Test to guide the antidepressant treatment of depressed patients, funded by P1vital Products Ltd, Manor House, Howbery Park, Wallingford, Oxfordshire, OX10 8BA from a European Union H2020 grant.

The purpose of the plan is to:

1. Ensure that the analysis is appropriate for the aims of the trial, reflects good statistical practice, and that interpretation of a priori and post hoc analyses is appropriate.
2. Explain in detail how the data will be processed and analysed to enable others to perform the analysis in any eventuality.

Additional exploratory or auxiliary analyses of data not specified in the protocol are permitted, but fall outside the scope of this analysis plan (although such analyses would be expected to follow Good Statistical Practice, GSP). Such analyses will be labelled as exploratory.

The analysis strategy will be made available if required to journal editors or reviewers when manuscripts are submitted for publication. Additional analyses suggested by reviewers or editors will, if considered appropriate, be performed in accordance with the Statistical Analysis Plan (SAP), but if reported the source of such a post-hoc analysis will be declared.

Amendments to the SAP will be described and justified in the final report of the trial.

2. SYNOPSIS OF STUDY DESIGN AND PROCEDURES

2.1. Trial aims and objectives

The purpose of the trial is to *test the clinical effectiveness* and cost-effectiveness/cost-utility of the PReDicT Test when it is used to direct antidepressant treatment. The current document describes the analyses of outcomes related to clinical effectiveness. Cost-effectiveness and cost utility will be described in a separate document.

2.1.1. Primary objective

To determine whether use of the PReDicT Test to direct antidepressant treatment results in an increased proportion of depressed patients showing a response to treatment at week 8 compared to Treatment as Usual (TaU).

- Response is defined as a decrease of 50% or more from baseline (pre-treatment) Quick Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology - Self Report 16 (QIDS-SR-16) scores.

2.1.2. Secondary objectives

- To compare the change from baseline in QIDS-SR-16 scores (i.e. treated as a continuous variable) at week 8 between depressed patients receiving treatment directed by the PReDicT Test and those receiving TaU.
- To determine whether use of the PReDicT Test to direct antidepressant treatment results in an increased proportion of depressed patients showing a response to treatment at week 8 compared to TaU, where response is defined as a decrease of 50% or more from baseline Montgomery–Åsberg Depression Rating Scale (MADRS) scores.
- To determine whether use of the PReDicT Test to direct antidepressant treatment results in an increased proportion of depressed patients achieving remission at week 8 compared to TaU where remission is defined as a QIDS-SR-16 score of 5 or less.
- To determine whether use of the PReDicT Test to direct antidepressant treatment results in an increased proportion of depressed patients achieving remission at week 8 compared to TaU where remission is defined as a MADRS score of 7 or less.
- To compare the change from baseline in QIDS-SR-16 score (i.e. treated as a continuous variable) at week 12 between depressed patients receiving treatment directed by the PReDicT Test and those receiving TaU.
- To compare the change from baseline in QIDS-SR-16 score (i.e. treated as a continuous variable) at 24 and 48 weeks between depressed patients receiving treatment directed by the PReDicT Test and those receiving TaU.

2.1.3. Exploratory objectives

- To compare the change from baseline in GAD-7 score (i.e. treated as a continuous variable) at week 8 between depressed patients receiving treatment directed by the PReDicT Test and those receiving TaU.
 - GAD-7: Generalised Anxiety Disorder Questionnaire, 7 item version.
- To compare the change from baseline on the depression and anxiety items (analysed separately) of the QIDS-SR-16 at week 8 between depressed patients receiving treatment directed by the PReDicT Test and those receiving TaU.
- To determine the change in cognitive function (assessed using the Digit Symbol Substitution Test, DSST) from baseline to week 8 between depressed patients receiving treatment directed by the PReDicT Test and those receiving TaU.
- To compare the change from baseline in self-reported social and occupational functioning at weeks 8, 24 and 48 between depressed patients receiving treatment directed by the PReDicT Test and those receiving TaU.
 - Social and occupational functioning will be assessed by SAS-SR (screener version).
 - SAS-SR: Social Adjustment Scale – Self-Report (screener version).

2.2. Trial design and configuration

The study is a randomised, two-arm, multi-centre, open label, clinical investigation of a medical device, the PReDicT Test. It will be conducted in depressed patients in primary care settings in five European countries (UK, France, Spain, Germany and the Netherlands).

The study is divided into an 8 to 10 week clinical phase and a 40 week follow-up phase. Each participant will be in the study for a total of up to 48-50 weeks.

During the clinical phase, participants will attend between 2 and 4 study visits, depending on their study arm and their response to treatment. Some of these visits may be conducted by telephone. Participants will also complete weekly online questionnaires from home.

During the follow-up phase participants will complete online questionnaires from home every 4 weeks over a 40 week period. Study visits will not be required during the follow-up phase.

An electronic Patient Reported Outcomes (ePRO) system, accessed via a study website, will be used to collect questionnaire data and PReDicT Test responses. The ePRO system will be used to randomise participants and will issue email reminders to participants and study researchers when study-related activities are due.

A total study duration of 30 months is planned (clinical phase and follow-up phase). The total duration of the clinical phase is expected to last approximately 18 months.

The study will enrol approximately 1200 participants, 600 per study arm. Each participating country is planned to enrol at least 150 participants. Based on data from the pilot study, approximately 1500 participants will be screened to enrol approximately 1200 participants, with the goal of having complete data (defined as participants who provide the data required for the primary analysis; QIDS-SR-16 scores at baseline and week 8) from 776 participants.

2.3. Trial centres

Number of trial centres in the five European countries (note that it is likely that some centres listed will not have recruited any patients by the end of the study making the final number of centres lower):

United Kingdom: 30

France: 1

Spain: 9

Germany: 21

Netherlands: 24

2.4. Eligibility criteria

2.4.1. Inclusion criteria

Potential participants will be included if they meet the following criteria:

- Male or female and aged between 18 and 70 inclusive¹.
- Diagnosed with a depressive episode by a physician (either first episode or recurrent) and requiring treatment with a selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRI) medication (excluding fluoxetine²).
- Prescribed an SSRI by a physician for the treatment of depression within the 7 days prior to Visit 1, but has not yet started taking the medication.
- Is intending to start SSRI treatment within 7 days of Visit 1.
- Willing and able to comply with study procedures.
- Able to give written informed consent in the study site's national language and has signed the informed consent form prior to the first study-related procedure.

2.4.2. Exclusion criteria

Potential participants will be excluded if they meet the following criteria:

- Previous history of mania.
- Is currently taking an antidepressant medication or has stopped antidepressant treatment within 2 weeks prior to Visit 1.
- Requires immediate referral to alternative mental health services (e.g. where a patient seen in primary care is referred to secondary care services).
- Presents to a physician with significant current suicidal intent requiring enhanced care.
- Is employed directly by the Investigator or is related to the Investigator.
- Currently taking part in another interventional clinical study which in the opinion of the investigator is likely to interfere with the objectives of the current study³.

¹ Due to age-related changes in drug metabolism, patients aged over 70 often require a different antidepressant regime to that used in this study.

² Fluoxetine has an elimination half-life of 4-6 days and its active metabolite, norfluoxetine, has an elimination half-life of 4-16 days. Thus the drug would be insufficiently washed out to allow an adequate assessment of any new treatment after one week.

³ Interventional studies include any study involving administration of a study drug or use of a medical device. Interventional studies do not include observational studies, post marketing surveillance, clinical audits or service evaluations.

2.5. Description of interventions

2.5.1 Brief Description of the Study Device:

There will be no study drugs prescribed as part of this clinical study. Eligible participants must have been prescribed an antidepressant (of the SSRI class) by their physician prior to study entry. The decision to start antidepressant treatment will be independent of study participation.

The PReDicT Test is a computer software application. It is CE marked and is categorised as a Class I medical device. The PReDicT Test consists of the QIDS-SR-16 questionnaire, a facial recognition task, and a proprietary prediction algorithm. The PReDicT Test will be accessed online using a standard web browser. It takes approximately 15 minutes to complete. Results, indicating response or non-response to antidepressant treatment, are available immediately on completion of the test. Test results will only be provided to the study researcher/physician when appropriate and will not be provided to participants.

2.5.2 Brief description of the planned intervention:

The study is divided into an 8 to 10 week clinical phase and a 40 week follow up phase (note, only follow up data up to week 24 will be included in the report to the funders as follow up data collected after this point will be collected after this report is due, and will be analysed fully following study completion).

Clinical Phase

During the Clinical phase, all patients will attend a screening visit. The eligible patients who provide consent will be randomly allocated to either the PReDicT arm or the TaU arm of the study and all patients will complete the PReDicT test before taking their medication.

- Participants in the PReDicT arm will complete the PReDicT Test again at week 1. If the PReDicT Test indicates non-response to drug the participant will also complete the PReDicT Test at week 2. PReDicT Test results will be provided to the prescribing physician for participants in the PReDicT arm. Antidepressant treatment should be changed by the prescribing physician (in accordance with locally appropriate guidelines and clinical judgement) when the PReDicT Test indicates non-response to drug.
- Participants in the TaU arm will complete the PReDicT Test again at week 1. PReDicT Test results will not be provided to the prescribing physician for participants in the TaU arm. Any change made to treatment by the prescribing physician will be based only on TaU (e.g. a change in drug treatment due to undesirable side effects).

During the clinical phase, participants will attend between 2 and 4 study visits, depending on which study arm they have been randomised to and their response to treatment. Some of these visits may be conducted by telephone. Participants will also complete weekly online questionnaires from home.

At week 8 all participants will undergo clinical evaluation of their response to treatment using questionnaires and assessments. They will also be asked to complete a Patient Acceptability Questionnaire.

Follow-Up Phase

During the follow-up phase participants will complete online questionnaires from home every 4 weeks

over a 40 week period. Clinic visits will not be required during the follow-up phase.

2.6. Randomisation procedures

2.6.1 Randomising procedure

Participants who meet the entry criteria at Visit 1 (baseline) will be randomised into one of the two study arms. Randomisation is carried out by the ePRO system. A study researcher will register each participant online. Registration details include the participant's unique screening number, first name, surname, gender and date of birth. The ePRO system will assign the participant a unique user ID. The participant will then be prompted to create an online account and to complete the PReDicT Test (PReDicT #1). The ePRO system will then randomise the participant to one of the two study arms. After randomisation, the study researcher will not tell the participant which study arm they are assigned. The study researcher will remind the participant that they will complete the PReDicT Test at least once and possibly on two further occasions and that they will be informed by the study team if a change in treatment is necessary. This information will have been provided previously in the ICF. The study **cannot be blinded** to a higher level (within the various study centres) as the study researchers and physicians will be aware of which participants are assigned to the PReDicT arm when the PReDicT #1 Test result is provided.

2.6.2 Randomisation ratio and stratification

Participants will be randomised into the PReDicT arm or the TaU arm using a 1:1 overall ratio. Randomisation will be **stratified** by study country and **minimised** by: a) gender (male/female), b) age (18-45 and 45-70) and c) baseline depression severity. Baseline depression severity will be calculated by the study software using QIDS-SR-16 scores. This will be categorised as mild/moderate (score 6-15) and severe/very severe (score of 16 or above).

The first 110 participants will be assigned to the PReDicT arm or the TaU arm in a 1:10 ratio. During this phase minimisation will not be used. After this the **minimisation** procedure will be applied, with minimisation being followed in 66% of cases. This will result in a 1:1 overall ratio across the duration of the study. The rationale for predominantly recruiting into the TaU arm early in the study is that the first 100 participants recruited into the TaU arm will be used to further refine the algorithm used to guide treatment. This additional refinement is desirable as the algorithm has previously been trained on data from participants in the UK only.

The randomisation program will be incorporated into the ePRO system and will be independently validated. The trial configuration and a schedule of procedures and stages are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Outline of Study Design

2.7. Sample size and justification

Sample size estimations suggest that 776 participants completed to week 8 are required.

The sample size was determined based on a minimum clinically relevant effect size (i.e. the difference in effect size between the TaU and PReDicT arms) which was set at 10% for the primary outcome (response at 8 weeks measured using the QIDS-SR-16). The baseline response rate in the TaU group was estimated, based on data from the pilot study, at 40%. Adding the minimum clinically relevant effect of guided treatment of 10% to this value results in a response rate of 50% in the PReDicT guided arm. Setting alpha at two tailed 0.05 and power at 80% indicates that a total sample size of 776 participants with primary

outcome data (388 per group) would be required to detect the specified minimum clinically relevant difference of 10%. Sample size calculations were performed in Stata 14 (StataCorp, College Station, Tex., USA).

The likely effect size of the intervention can be estimated from the data collected during the pilot study, which assessed the sensitivity and specificity of the components of the PReDicT test. This study found a figure of 0.75 for both sensitivity and specificity of the test. Assuming a reduced performance of the test when it is applied in the current multi-country study (setting sensitivity and specificity to 0.7) suggests an expected response rate of 0.548 in the PReDicT arm. If accurate, this estimate indicates that the difference in the primary outcome between the two study arms will be substantially higher than the minimum clinically relevant effect used in the sample size calculation above suggesting the sample size of 776 is an overestimate. However, the accuracy of this estimate is limited by marked uncertainty in a number of the parameters used in its calculation, such as the degree to which the effect of treatment is likely to vary between countries. This uncertainty in the expected effect size of the PReDicT Test will be addressed in a planned interim analysis which will be performed after primary outcome data from 300 participants have been collected. This analysis will estimate the effect size of the intervention and the degree to which this varies between countries, as well as assessing the performance (i.e. recruitment and retention of participants) in each country. The results of this interim analysis will be interpreted by an independent data monitoring committee to determine whether the final sample size should be modified [1].

The expected attrition rate across the first 8 weeks of the trial, based on data from the pilot study, is 33%. Participants withdrawn from the study will not be replaced, thus approximately 1200 participants will be enrolled to ensure 776 participants complete the study (NB trial completers are defined as participants who have fully completed the QIDS-SR-16 at both baseline and week 8, providing the required data for the primary analysis).

2.8. Blinding and breaking of blind

Study participants, study site staff and sponsor **cannot be blinded** to group allocation in the current study as the allocation determines the procedures which must be completed and thus group allocation is apparent from the data points available for each participant. However the trial statistician will be kept blinded to the allocation.

2.9. Trial committees

A number of committees will be assembled to ensure the proper management and conduct of the trial, and to uphold the safety and well-being of participants. The general purpose, responsibilities and structures of the committees are described in the protocol. However each committee will develop its own rules and procedures which may evolve over the course of the study. Note that, as this is not a blinded study, the committees listed below will have access to the study data.

2.9.1 Trial Management Group

The Trial Management Group (TMG) will oversee the operational aspects of the trial. The TMG will meet regularly to review the progress of the trial and address any issues arising.

2.9.2 Executive Steering Committee

The Executive Steering Committee (ESC) will monitor, review and supervise the progress of the trial. The committee will include work package leads for all aspects of the PReDicT project; Product development of the PReDicT test (work package 1), the current clinical trial (work package 2),

commercialisation of the PReDicT test (work package 3), stakeholder engagement for and dissemination of the PReDicT test (work package 4), and overall project management (work package 5). The ESC will consider reports from the DMC when making recommendations. The Executive Steering Committee will monitor study data (and DMC reports) to consider safety and efficacy indications. The ESC may recommend discontinuation of the study if significant ethical or safety concerns arise.

2.9.3 Data Monitoring Committee

An independent Data Monitoring Committee will be established with access to data to provide independent review and recommendations in the light of potential treatment effect or questions of safety. The DMC will meet or teleconference prior to the first 110 participants providing primary outcome data and will agree terms of reference and a provisional meeting or teleconferencing schedule. The DMC will be provided with the interim analysis results, collected after data on approximately 300 patients has been collected. The DMC will provide advice on whether to adjust sample size as well as on how study performance (i.e. recruitment and dropout rates, protocol violations) may be improved in the various study countries and on safety (i.e. device deficiency) issues identified.

2.10. Outcome measures

2.10.1. Primary outcome

- Response defined by $\geq 50\%$ decrease in QIDS-SR-16 score from week 0 (baseline) to week 8.

2.10.2. Secondary outcomes

- Change in MADRS score from week 0 (baseline) to week 8.
- Change in QIDS-SR-16 scores from week 0 (baseline) to week 8, 12, 24 and 48 weeks.
- Response to treatment defined by MADRS 8 week score:
 - Response = decrease $\geq 50\%$ baseline score
- Remission defined by QIDS-SR-16 score and MADRS score using the following cut-offs:
 - Remission = QIDS-SR-16 score ≤ 5 at week 8, 12, 24 and 48
 - Remission = MADRS score ≤ 7 at week 8, 12, 24, and 48

2.10.3. Exploratory outcomes

- QIDS-SR-16 change scores for depression and anxiety items (only) from week 0 (baseline) to 8, 12, 24 and 48.
- GAD-7 change scores from weeks 0 (baseline) to 8.
- DSST change scores from weeks 0 (baseline) to 8.
- SAS-SR (screeener version) change scores from weeks 0 (baseline) to, 8, 24 and 48.

2.10.4. Collection time of each measure

For all patients demographic, clinic effectiveness outcome measures and other relevant measures use in this trial, the collection time could be found from table 1 and table 2.

Table 1: Time and Events Table – Clinical Phase Activities (inserted from protocol appendix 1)

	Visit 1: Screening and PReDicT #1	Treatment start date	PReDicT #2	Visit 2 (if required)	Change of Dose start date ¹ (if required)	PReDicT #3 (if required)	Visit 3 (if required)	Change of medication start date ² (if required)	Visit 4 ³
Requirements for timing of event	Within 7 days of initial consultation	Day 0	≥ 7 days after Day 0			≥ 7 days after changed dose			≥ 8-10 weeks after Day 0
Preferred timing		Day 0	7-9 days after Day 0	0-1 day after PReDicT #2	0-1 day after Visit 2	7-9 days after changed dose	0-1 day after PReDicT #3	0-1 day after Visit 3	8 weeks after Day 0
Informed consent	X								
Demographics	X								
Medical history	X								
Medication history	X								
Entry criteria check	X								
MADRS	X								X
Change in antidepressant (AD) medication agreed				X ¹			X ²		
AD medication compliance									X
Review of concomitant medication									X

Review of AEs, ADEs and device deficiencies	X								X
ePRO Activities									
Researcher registers patient online	X								
Participant creates online account	X								
Researcher enters AD details	X			X ¹			X ²		
Participant enters AD start date		X			X			X	
PReDicT Test	X		X			X ¹			
QIDS-SR-16	X ⁴	Completed weekly, starting 7 days after Day 0. Not required if PReDicT test is completed in same week							X ^{4,5}
Randomisation	X								
EQ-5D-5L ⁶	X								X ⁵
HEQ ⁶	X								X ⁵
OxCAP-MH (UK & Germany only)	X ⁷								X ⁵
SAS-SR (screener version)	X ⁷								X ⁵
GAD-7	X ⁷								X ⁵
DSST	X ⁷								X ⁵
Patient Acceptability Questionnaire									X ⁵

Note: Time and Events Table – Clinical Phase Activities - Key

1. If PReDicT #2 outcome = non-response, physician decides if antidepressant will be changed. PReDicT #3 will be completed.
2. If PReDicT #3 outcome = non-response physician decides if antidepressant will be changed.
3. Participants who withdraw will be invited to complete (in order of preference): Visit 4 (at 8 week time point); Visit 4 online questionnaires (from home at 8 week time point); Patient Acceptability Questionnaire (immediately); no additional data.
4. QIDS-SR-16 is included in the PReDicT test.
5. Permissible for participant to complete online assessment at home before or after Visit 4.
6. Questionnaire also completed online 4 weeks after Day 0.
7. Permissible for participant to complete online assessment at home prior to antidepressant treatment start date.

Table 2: Time and Events Table – Follow-Up Phase Activities (inserted from protocol appendix 2)

Online Activity	Follow-Up #1	Follow-Up #2	Follow-Up #3	Follow-Up #4	Follow-Up #5	Follow-Up #6	Follow-Up #7	Follow-Up #8	Follow-Up #9	Follow-Up #10
Timing of Activity ¹	Week 12 i.e. 4 weeks after Visit 4	Week 16	Week 20	Week 24	Week 28	Week 32	Week 36	Week 40	Week 44	Week 48
QIDS-SR-16	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
EQ-5D-5L	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
HEQ	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
OxCAP-MH (UK and Germany only)				X						X
SAS-SR (screeener version)				X						X

Note: Key

1. Data can be captured any time up to the due date of the next Follow-Up.

2.11. Interim analysis

An interim analysis will be performed when primary outcome data from approximately 300 patients is available. The interim analysis will assess recruitment and dropout rates within each country, adherence to the study protocol and safety in terms of adverse events and device deficiencies in the two study arms. As the degree of clustering occurring in between study sites and countries is not known, it is unclear if the sample size calculation and primary analysis should account for the cluster effects at the level of individual study sites and/or countries or all possible level. This question will be addressed in the interim analysis by fitting multilevel models (MLM) exploring the clustering effects at each of the study site and country level. The significance of the clustering effect will be used to inform sample size adjustment and future primary analysis. The interim analysis will also assess the effect size estimate of the difference between the PReDicT arm and TaU arm on the primary outcome analysis will be conducted with group status blinded to the independent trial statistician. Results of this interim analysis will be interpreted by an independent data monitoring committee to determine whether the final sample size should be modified [2] (note the independent data monitoring committee will have access to unblinded data and results).

As the treatments used in the study are licensed antidepressants rather than a novel treatment, formal stopping criteria will not be employed. Study enrolment will continue while the interim analysis is being performed.

3. GENERAL ANALYSIS CONSIDERATIONS

3.1. Overview of analyses

Multilevel modelling will be used for the analyses (see sections 6.2-6.5 for a detailed description of the statistical models to be used). This will include logistic regression for categorical variables, linear regression for continuous variables and repeated measures approaches where appropriate. The stratification (country and minimisation factors (age, gender, baseline depression severity) will be included in the models.

3.2. Analysis samples

All analyses will be conducted on an intention to treat (ITT) basis. The ITT analysis sample is defined as all randomised participants.

Further exploratory analyses on primary, secondary and exploratory objectives may be conducted on the **per-protocol set**. The **per-protocol set** is defined as all randomised participants in which the relevant outcomes have been collected who have not significantly deviated from the CIP. Review of significant CIP deviations will be performed by the study Investigators prior to analyses and the list of patient included in per-protocol analysis set will be provided to trial statistician.

3.3. Derived variables

Two kinds of outcome measures will be derived from the QIDS-SR-16 and MADRS baseline and week 8 scores, response and remission.

Response:

- Decrease of more than 50% from baseline QIDS-SR-16 score at week 8 measure. This is the primary outcome measure.
- Decrease of more than 50% from baseline MADRS score at week 8 measure.

Remission:

- QIDS-SR-16 at week 8 score ≤ 5 .
- MADRS at week 8 score ≤ 7 .

Additionally, age will be calculated with date of birth and visit 1 time information.

3.4. Procedures for missing data

Missing values in all outcomes will be inspected and reported across treatment group and follow-up time. For variables measured at baseline and week 8 only, multilevel logistic regression will be performed to explore the effects of treatment and baseline measure on 'missingness' of each outcome with country and clinical site as higher level units. For variables repeatedly measured more than 2 times, multilevel logistic regression will be performed to explore the effects of treatment and baseline measure on 'missingness' of each outcome, with country, clinic site as higher level unit, in addition to accounting the cluster effect due to data repeatedly collected. Logistic regression results will be used to inform imputing missingness using multiple imputation procedure under Missing At Random (MAR) assumption [3] REALCOM or MLwiN will be used to perform multiple imputation where appropriate [4 5]. For each outcomes having missingness, 15 datasets will be generated [6].

3.5. Timing of Study Analyses

The primary study analysis (i.e. of outcome measures collected up to week 8) will be performed when all participants have completed the clinical phase of the study (week 0 to week 8). In the event that the target recruitment number is not met by the end of the study, this analysis (i.e. up to week 8) will be performed on all eligible participants recruited into the study up to the point that the study was closed. This analysis will be performed as described above and will assess all objectives evaluating outcomes up to week 8 of the study. The rationale for the inclusion of this analysis is that it ensures that the long follow-up phase does not unduly delay the reporting of the clinical phase study results. All other analyses will be performed when the data collection required to perform that analysis is complete (NB for repeated measures, when all repeated measures data is available). This will be after completion of the 24 week data collection for the main follow up analysis (to be provided to the funder) and after all data collection for the final data analysis.

3.6. Level of Statistical Significance

Analysis of the primary endpoint will be considered significant using a cut off of two sided $P < 0.05$. The same cut off will be used in secondary, health economic and exploratory analyses. No correction for multiplicity of analyses will be made for the secondary and exploratory analyses, as there is only one primary outcome and all secondary and exploratory outcomes are supportive, plus no conclusion on treatment effectiveness will be drawn from the planned interim analysis [7].

4. DESCRIPTION OF PARTICIPANT CHARACTERISTICS**4.1. Participant flow**

A CONSORT flow chart will be generated to summarise participant flow through the study

4.2. Baseline characteristics

Continuous data that are approximately normally distributed will be summarised in terms of the mean, standard deviation, median, minimum, maximum and number of observations. Skewed data will be presented in terms of the maximum, upper quartile, median, lower quartile, minimum and number of observations. Categorical data will be summarised in terms of frequency counts and percentages. These data will be summarized within each group (PREdicT and TAU) as well as by country (UK, France, Germany, the Netherlands, Spain, and Germany). Differences in patient characteristics between study completers and those who have withdrawn will be summarised. Demographic variables (e.g. age, sex, ethnicity, height and weight) will be summarised by treatment group and overall

- Possible effect modifiers (e.g. years of education) will be summarised by treatment group and overall.
- Disease factors (presence of family history of depression) will be summarised by treatment group and overall Comorbidity: previous and concomitant illness will be summarised by treatment group and overall.
- Medication: previous and concomitant medication will be summarised by treatment group and overall.
- Provide details of the coding dictionary that is to be used for concomitant medication.

5. ASSESSMENT OF STUDY QUALITY

Before database lock a summary of randomisation and protocol deviations will be generated from review of study data that does not include group allocation. This will be co-ordinated by P1vital and agreed in meetings involving study sites. After database lock assessment of adherence will be completed in a similar manner (NB adherence to PREdicT test guidance can only be assessed on unblinded data).

5.1. Randomisation

Number of participants randomised in error and the reason for the error will be provided.

5.2. Adherence

Patients in the PREdicT arm, whose treatment was changed against the recommendation of the PREdicT test (i.e. treatment changed when test indicated no change needed or treatment not changed when test indicated change was required), will be listed including details of the PREdicT response, the subsequent treatment and why this occurred.

5.3. Protocol deviations

Major protocol deviations will be listed and agreed before database lock.

5.4. Changes made to the planned statistical analyses

N/A

6. ANALYSIS OF EFFECTIVENESS/EFFICACY

6.1. Summary of primary and secondary outcomes

Primary outcome

- The response defined by $\geq 50\%$ decrease in QIDS-SR-16 score from week 0 (baseline) to week 8. Coded as Binary variable.

Secondary outcome include:

- Change in MADRS score from week 0 (baseline) to week 8.
- Change in QIDS-16-SR scores from week 0 (baseline) to week 8, 12, 24 and week 48.

The change score are expected being normally distributed, subjected to normality check with exploratory data analysis. Skewed measure will be transformed to data with symmetric shape for modelling if needed. The same principle will be applied to exploratory outcomes.

Response defined by $\geq 50\%$ decrease in MADRS score from week 0 (baseline) to week 8, coded as Binary variable.

Remission defined by:

- QIDS-16-SR at week 8 score ≤ 5 .
- MADRS at week 8 score ≤ 7 , respectively.

Exploratory outcome include:

- Change in QIDS-SR-16 scores for depression and anxiety items (only) score from week 0 (baseline) to week 8.
- Change in GAD-7 scores from week 0 (baseline) to week 8.
- Change in DSST scores from week 0 (baseline) to week 8.
- Change in SAS-SR (screening version) scores from week 0 (baseline) to week 8, 24 and 48.

6.2. Primary analysis

Multilevel logistic regression with age, gender, and baseline depression score included as covariates [7], country and clinic site as higher level unit to quantify the treatment effect being presented as Odds Ratio (OR) and its 95% Confidence Interval (CI) [8]. The model could be written as:

$$\text{Logit}(p_{ijk}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{group}_{ijk} + \sum \beta_{ijkh}(\text{age, gender, baseline depression}) + v_k + \mu_{jk} \quad (1)$$

Exponentiated β_1 (95%CI) is the treatment effect estimate expressed as Odds Ratio (95%CI), i = patient ID, j = Clinical site ID, k =country ID, h is covariate variable ID. v_k is country level deviate, μ_{jk} is clinical site level deviate. The variability at each level will be first explored with non-statistically significant variance to be fixed for model parsimony purpose. Age, gender, baseline depression will have to be included as covariate due to minimisation procedure [7].

6.3. Secondary/sensitivity analysis of primary outcome

Primary analysis mode will be conducted on observed data only, and per-protocol analysis (if observed data is different from PPA), as sensitivity analyses to check the robustness of primary analysis results to missingness influence.

If positive treatment effects are found, we will then explore the treatment heterogeneity of treatment effects across countries, as per ICH E9 and ICH E17 suggestion [9 10]. The treatment effect estimate parameter β_1 in primary analysis modelling will be set random (β_{1k}) across country level, conditional on significant country level variance evidenced. The possible modelling will be:

$$\text{Logit}(p_{ijk}) = \beta_0 + \beta_{1k}\text{group}_{ijk} + \sum \beta_{ijkh}(\text{age, gender, baseline depression}) + v_k + \mu_{jk} \quad (1a)$$

Forest plot will be used to present country-specific treatment effects estimates and their 95%CI.

6.4. Secondary outcomes

For binary outcomes measured including response defined by MADRS score reduction from baseline to week 8 and remission status, the models used to quantify treatment effects are identical to primary analytic model.

$$\text{Logit}(p_{ijk}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{group}_{ijk} + \sum \beta_{ijkh}(\text{age, gender, baseline depression}) + v_k + \mu_{jk} \quad (2)$$

For continuous outcomes measured with one flow-up, multilevel linear regression will be used to quantify the treatment effect. The MLM linear model could be written as:

$$Y_{ijk} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{group}_{ijk} + \sum \beta_{ijkh}(\text{baseline measure, age, gender, baseline depression}) + v_k + \mu_{jk} + e_{ijk} \quad (3)$$

With Y_{ijk} is the change score of outcome for patient i from site j of country k . e_{ijk} is the residual quantity of change score of outcome measure for patient i from site j of country k not capture by modelling. v_k and μ_{jk} have same meaning as shown in primary analysis modelling.

For continuous outcome measured with two more follow-ups, multilevel linear regression will be used to quantify the treatment effect, with categorical time included as additional covariate. This MLM linear model could be written as:

$$Y_{tijk} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{group}_{ijk} + \sum \beta_{tijkh}(\text{dummy time and interaction with group, baseline measure, age, gender, baseline depression}) + v_k + \mu_{jk} + z_{ijk} + e_{tijk} \quad (4)$$

Where Y_{tijk} is the change score of outcome at t -th time for patient i from site j of country k , t is the t -th time, z_{ijk} is deviant of i -th people's t -th measure from overall estimate, other parameters have same meaning as parameters in equation (3)

For PAQ which was only measured at week 8, MLM regression (3) will be used but no baseline included in covariate list. The equation could be written as:

$$Y_{ijk} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{group}_{ijk} + \sum \beta_{ijkh}(\text{age, gender, baseline depression}) + v_k + \mu_{jk} + e_{ijk} \quad (5)$$

As for primary outcome, PPA and observed data only analysis will additionally performed.

6.5. Exploratory outcome

Modelling procedure for exploratory outcomes will be identical to modelling for secondary outcomes.

7. ANALYSIS OF SAFETY

7.1. Adverse events

Adverse event summaries will be based upon the number of participants reporting adverse events and the number of events reported per participant.

8. ADDITIONAL EXPLANATORY ANALYSES

The underlying mechanistic logic of the PReDicT study is that the likelihood of patient response is identified using the test, which when suggestive of a non-response, prompts the clinician to change the prescribed antidepressant, which in turn improves outcome. Additional explanatory analyses will be conducted to test this logic by testing, for example, the difference in medication change rates between groups at week 8 as well as across the longer follow up period. These analyses will be exploratory in nature and will be used solely to examine the mechanism of the intervention rather than to make claims of efficacy.

9. FINAL REPORT TABLES AND FIGURES

Table 1. Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Randomised Sample (separate tables will be provided for all participants and per country)

	TaU (N =)	PReDicT (N=)
Age: mean (range)		
Gender, female: n (%)		
Race		
QIDS-16-SR, mean (SD, range)		
MADRS, mean (SD, range)		
GAD-7, mean (SD, range)		
Do you have a first degree relative with a history of depression?		
DSST score		
Total MADRS Score (Baseline)		

Table 2. Results of multilevel Logistic regression: OR (95% CI)

	TaU	PReDicT	Group comparison	
	P (95%CI)	P (95%CI)	OR (95%CI)	P value
Response				
QIDS-SR-16				
MADRS				
Remission				
QIDS-SR-16				
MADRS				

Table 3. Results of multilevel modelling of change score (95% CI) from baseline and group difference (95% CI)

	TaU	PReDicT	Group comparison	
	Mean change from baseline (95%CI)	Mean change from baseline (95%CI)	Change difference (95%CI)	P value
QIDS-SR-16				
8 weeks				
12 weeks				
24 weeks				
48 weeks				
Other normally distributed measures				

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HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	APPROVAL DATE	CHANGE
0.1		Original - working draft
1.0	21 Nov 2017	Approved for Interim Analysis
2.0	25 April 2018	Final formatting for online publication